

POLAND

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“SULAYMAN” CASTLE**Ismailov Tokhirjon Khushnubek ugli**

Teacher of Mamun University

E-mail: ismailovtohir4349@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8571-3653>**Khusainbaeva Rabiyajon Khujabaevna**

Mamun University

Philology and language teaching: 3rd year English language student

E-mail: xusainboyevvarobiya@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14061893>

Sulayman Castle (*Hazorasp Castle, Hazorasp City Castle Wall*) is one of the oldest castles in Hazorasp District, Khorezm Region of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Today, the fortress dating back to the IV-II centuries BC is located in the Sulayman Qala neighborhood.

The "Hazorasp" fortress, which played a very important role in the life of the Khorezm oasis, was once a large economic, social and political center. The castle is located in the Hazorasp district of the Khorezm region, and it is said that it was the residence of a person who lived and ruled in the 5th century AD. The walls of the castle have been preserved to this day, and in order to ensure its safety, the bottom of the walls of the castle was surrounded by a lake. The local people named this lake "*Oydin Lake*". The unique aspect of the lake is that it is constantly supplied with fresh water. According to historical sources, there was once an underground road under the lake. The hill at the top of the castle was used for astronomical observations.

The "*Hazorasp*" fortress was not only the southern gate of Khorezm, but also a military-strategic fortification. This fortress resisted any attack coming from the south of the oasis, and in many cases, the enemy, knowing that he was not strong enough to conquer Khorezm, was forced to retreat from this place. Juvaini, who is the author of a great work called "*History of Jahangosha*", says: "*Sultan Makhmud, the head of the Ghaznavid state, during his third campaign to Khorezm, subdued the strong fortress of Hazorasp only after a two-month heavy siege*" - he writes.

Here, there are a number of myths and legends about the construction of the "*Hazorasp*" fortress, and ethnographers and local history researchers believe that the name of the city is related to the name of the "*Khazar*" and "*Os*" tribes that once lived here they put forward a not far-fetched idea. Because the name of the stream, which is preserved to this day and passes near the castle, is also

called "Hosoyop", and it supplied the lands of the Os tribe with water several thousand years ago.

The first written information about Hazorasp is found in Abu Rayhan Beruni's *"Memorials from Ancient Generations"*. The famous historian al-Tabari noted that in Khorezm, which was conquered by the Arabs in 712, there were three large cities - Kat, Gurganj and Hazorasp. Another great Arab historian, al-Istahri, noted that several streams flowed near the fortress and the name of one of them was Hazorasp.

In 1219-1221, the Mongol-Tatars conquered Central Asia and crushed the Khorezmshah Anushtagini empire. On the eve of this invasion, the Arab traveler Ibrahim ibn Yakut, who was in Hazorasp, wrote the following: *"This is an impregnable fortress and a very beautiful city. It is surrounded by water like an island. There is only one entrance to the fortress, and it is also made by Khorezm. The journey between them is three days. It is located on a flat land and has many markets and merchants. The population is rich."*

On October 4, 2019, by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Suleiman Castle was included in the national list of immovable property objects of tangible cultural heritage and was taken under state protection. Currently, the Cultural Heritage Department of Khorezm Region is state property based on the right of operational management.

